

**From fear to fun: an experimental investigation on the joint effect of emotional appeals
and social norm elements in advertising on sustainable eating intention**

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Abstract

This scientific paper explores the influence of emotional appeals and social norm elements on individuals' sustainable eating intentions. The study addresses the urgent need for sustainable practices in the food sector to mitigate environmental impact and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Specifically, the research investigates the effects of fear and humor appeals compared to no appeals in advertisements on sustainable eating intention. Additionally, it examines the moderating role of descriptive and injunctive norm elements. A between-groups 3x2 experimental design is employed, involving a diverse sample of adults ($N = 197$) ranging from 18 to 65 years old, recruited through a convenience sampling technique. The experiment consisted of an online questionnaire exposing participants to one of the research stimuli and measuring all relevant variables. A Two-Way ANOVA test shows no difference in the use of fear appeals, humor appeals, or no appeals in ads aiming to influence sustainable eating intention. Moreover, the study demonstrates that the interaction between appeal type and social norm elements does not affect sustainable eating intention. By filling gaps in previous research, this study contributes valuable insights to the field and examines the use of emotional appeals and social norms in promoting sustainable eating behaviors.

Keywords: sustainable eating, advertising, emotional appeals, fear appeals, humor appeals, social norms elements, behavioral intention

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By 2050, The European Union aims to reach net-zero emissions through a strategy that addresses the food sector and its consumers (European Climate Pact, 2022). The reason behind this urgency is simple, but often ignored. What we eat does have an impact on the environment.

Sustainability is a multi-faceted concept not often associated with diets and eating behaviors by consumers. However, the food-production processes involve great amounts of water usage, with animal-based nourishments requiring the most. Plant-based diets have been regarded as the most sustainable options to reduce anthropogenic climate change emissions, largely caused by meat-based production (Beverland, 2014). Moreover, food consumption has been classified as one of the major causes of greenhouse gas (GHG) footprint (USDA, 2022). Sustainable eating can be defined as the consumption of food produced in ways that minimize the harmful impact of pollutants and emissions on the environment (Vermeir et al., 2020). This makes it a socially relevant behavior, emphasizing the importance of finding ways to promote more sustainable diets to reduce emissions and counter the climate change crisis.

Given the overabundance of food production and the great accessibility to mass-produced nourishments, people commonly do not associate their eating habits with their potentially harmful impact on the environment (Beverland, 2014). People's decision-making processes are, however, not only influenced by their conscious reflections about the subject matter but also by heuristics that may shift their intentions to adopt a certain behavior (Dietrich, 2010). A strategy that is used by advertisers consists of including appeals that may trigger an emotional response in the receiver (Holbrook & O'Shaughnessy, 1984). Fear and humor appeals are both strong predictors of behavioral intention (Pressgrove et al., 2021). However, there is little knowledge on whether opposite emotions (i.e., negative and positive) elicited by these two appeals would differently affect people's sustainable eating intention.

Fear appeals might, for instance, consist of unsympathetic information or visual cues aimed at triggering one's sense of urgency toward changing a specific behavior to prevent the

risk from happening or getting worse (Skurka et al., 2018; Witte, 1994). Fear is a complex emotion, but at the same time, it can have a powerful influence on behavioral change (Leventhal, 1971; Van Breda et al., 2023). On the other hand, humor appeals are attempts to trigger positive emotions (e.g., joy, happiness) and a generally good mood in the receiver, often together with laughter (Meyer & Venette, 2017; Van Der Pligt & Vliek, 2016). There are, however, downsides associated with humor, as its effectiveness depends to a large extent on the audience's perceptions and prior cognitive state (Meyer, 2000). For example, people who perceive incongruence between the use of humor and a certain subject matter may respond negatively. Moreover, previous research has given little attention to the influence of humor appeals within the food sector, especially regarding sustainability, whilst fear appeals have more extensively been investigated (Jackson & Meah, 2019).

Existing studies have investigated the use of fear and humor appeals compared to having none in the context of pro-environmentally behaviors (i.e., intention to engage in climate change advocacy, climate change mitigation behaviors) (Skurka et al., 2018; Van Breda et al., 2023). Nevertheless, previous research lacks extensive knowledge about a comparison between the presence and the absence of emotional appeals – hence resulting in a more informative type of ad – and their effect on sustainable eating intention. Therefore, a control group (viz., no appeal in the ad) is included to make an advanced comparison.

Additionally, the moderating effect of social norm elements in the ad is part of the investigation of the current research. Social norms refer to ways our social environment influences our behaviors and are generally divided into descriptive and injunctive norms (Melnik et al., 2013). Descriptive norms refer to how other people's actual behavior sets the norm, while injunctive norms are rather tied to our belief of how the majority behaves, despite this does not necessarily reflect the truth (Melnik et al., 2013). The normative influence of social norms was proven to affect individuals' behavior in the sustainable domain (Pristl et al., 2021). Social norms are included as a moderator due to their normative influence, which can create cognitive dissonance between the emotions evoked by different appeals and a social group's dictated norms. Such dissonance is the result of an inconsistency between opposite cognitions (McKimmie, 2015). This could refer, in this study, to a discrepancy between a negative emotion aroused by a fear appeal and a positive one elicited

by a norm set by a social group. This potential ambivalence may alter the original effect of fear and humor appeals on sustainable eating intention. Therefore, social norms were chosen as a moderator to understand how they influence the relationship between emotional appeals and sustainable eating intention.

Social norms also influence individuals' decision-making processes (Sanfey et al., 2014). In the context of sustainable consumption, people's decision-making processes are, moreover, affected by their social responsibility, which encompasses the consideration of societal and environmental consequences (Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006). On the one hand, injunctive norms contribute to individuals' sense of social responsibility by reinforcing the idea that their decisions - which seek social approval - can have a positive impact on the broader society (Voisin et al., 2020). On the other hand, the prevalence of sustainable eating behaviors within a social group sets the norm (i.e., descriptive norm) and establishes a benchmark for behavior (Melnik et al., 2010). Observing others prioritizing sustainable eating in their food choices would create a sense of social responsibility and encourage individuals to consider the broader societal and environmental impacts of their eating habits (Voisin et al., 2020). Sustainable eating should therefore be regarded as a socially-relevant behavior, as people continuously respond to social and institutional norms when making their decisions about what they want to – and will – consume (Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006).

First, the current research aims to fill the mentioned gap by including social norm elements as a moderator and by furthermore demonstrating the relevance of social norms in the context of sustainable eating. Secondly, this study aims to evaluate and compare the use of two opposite emotional appeals within the context of sustainable eating, to compensate for the lack of research specifically about humor and fear appeals in the field.

Taking all that has been mentioned together, the following research question was formulated:

RQ: To what extent does the use of different appeal types (humor appeal vs. fear appeal vs. no appeal) in advertising about sustainable eating influence people's sustainable eating intention, and how does the relationship differ for different social norm elements in the ad (injunctive norm elements vs. descriptive norm elements)?

Theoretical Framework

Appeal types (in advertising) and sustainable eating intention

Fear appeals consist of persuasive messages that highlight the negative consequences of a certain behavior, thus eliciting fear (Jäger & Eisend, 2013). On the contrary, humor appeals provide a less obtrusive way of inducing positive emotions in the receivers, by presenting the message in a light-hearted manner (Jäger & Eisend, 2013). Fear appeals were selected because they are easily acknowledged and understood, at the same time generating more interest in the receiver rather than humor appeals (Tran et al., 2021). This mechanism may be explained by the extended parallel process model by Witte (1994). Fear is automatically triggered in the receivers of the risk information, which serves as a stimulus to generate immediate interest (Witte, 1994). Additionally, in promoting sustainable behaviors, negative appeals (e.g., fear appeals) are generally preferred as they are more powerful motivators than positive appeals (Van Breda et al., 2023). On the other hand, humor appeals have been recognized to be pervasive and influential (Meyer, 2000). Humor owns significant social value and can have incredible normative power. Concurrently, it often silently aims to challenge the existing norms while reinforcing the dynamics of a group that shares the same type of wittiness (Jackson & Meah, 2019).

The use of fear (vs. hope) appeals in health communication advertisements has a positive effect on healthy eating intentions, such that the more fear appeals are used, the stronger the intention to eat healthy food (Fariás, 2020). Healthy eating and sustainable eating are indeed two different concepts. However, both concepts underpin a similar objective, which is to encourage a shift from over-processed food towards more “green” options (e.g., plant-based foods) (Verbeke et al., 2017). Therefore, results from studies about healthy eating are deemed applicable to the inquiry of the current study. Additionally, Skurka et al. (2018) conducted an experimental study on the effect of fear and humor appeals on climate change activism intentions. The researchers found that exposure to both the fear and the humor appeals led to stronger intentions to change their behaviors than compared to viewing no appeals (Skurka et al., 2018). Consequently, viewing no appeals resulted to be the weakest predictor when compared to the presence of either one of the two appeals.

The dependent variable of the current study concerns a specific type of behavioral intention, aimed at encouraging more sustainable-oriented eating habits among consumers. Some concrete examples of adopting more sustainable eating patterns encompass: buying regional rather than imported food, reducing meat consumption, and preferring seasonal fruit and vegetables over non-seasonal ones (Tobler et al., 2011).

Humor appeals have been proven to secure the audience's attention, however, people are often distracted by the humorous features of the advertisement rather than concentrating on the content of the ad (Han & Stout, 2022). These findings suggest that, in situations where it is important to convey a clear message, humor appeals may not be a strong predictor of behavioral intention (Van Der Pligt & Vliek, 2016). Sustainable eating is an important issue at stake, hence it is fundamental not only to trigger positive emotions in the receivers but also to give proper attention to the symbolic and cultural meaning that is being conveyed (Parekh & Svenfelt, 2022). Therefore, the first hypothesis was generated:

H1: The use of fear appeals in ads about sustainable eating leads to a stronger sustainable eating intention compared to the use of humor appeals and no appeals.

Social norm elements as a moderator

The moderator of the current study refers to social norms, which are generally divided into descriptive and injunctive norms. While descriptive norms can be defined as others' actual behavior, injunctive norms are rather our impressions of how others behave and think we should behave (Melnyk et al., 2013). Social norms have a strong influence on behavioral intention, such that they display the great influence of social groups in an individual's environment (Park & Smith, 2007). In particular, researchers have acknowledged that the issue of sustainable eating is a positive social trend related to global social change and that its underlying mechanisms should be investigated (Ham et al., 2015).

Descriptive norms have been demonstrated to be more effective when people need behavioral guidance in situations of uncertainty and threat (Gelfand & Harrington, 2015). When fear appeals are communicated, the receiver may, to a certain extent, feel in a state of perceived risk and hesitation. Therefore, when exposed to fearful stimuli, people are more likely to rely on others' behaviors to fulfill their need for closure (i.e., the desire to reduce

ambiguity) (Gelfand & Harrington, 2015). Descriptive norms may serve as guidance for behavior when people feel hesitant or threatened (e.g. when exposed to a fear appeal). If, for example, the behavior of people who follow a sustainable diet is highlighted in a situation of uncertainty, individuals would likely rely on the norm set by others and mimic their behavior to contrast the presented threat. Therefore, this research expects that the interaction of descriptive norms elements and fear appeals will result in an increased sustainable eating intention.

On the other hand, humor has intrinsic social properties that make it generally regarded as a social phenomenon (Meyer, 2000). One of the two main functions of humor is to give a sense of unification within a group, as people who are perceived to appreciate humor are usually seen as more desirable to be around (Meyer, 2000). Research by Mifdal (2022) demonstrated that humor appeals work more effectively in triggering a response when injunctive norms rather than descriptive norms are used to motivate people to change their behavior. Additionally, injunctive norms drive individuals to research for social approval (Melnik et al., 2013), and this may be reached by adhering to the same type of humor within a specific group. Therefore, it is expected that including humor together with injunctive norm elements will enact a positive reaction in the receiver, as the combination of the two will reinforce their perception to adhere to the status quo (Meyer, 2000).

Additionally, the interaction effect between social norms appeals and the presence (vs. absence) of fear appeals on behavioral intention was significant in the study by Liu et al. (2022). More specifically, the authors found that behavioral intention would become stronger when group cues were associated with the absence - rather than presence - of fear appeals (Liu et al., 2022). Group cues (e.g., feedback from others) refer to the observable or perceived signals within a social group that influence individuals' behavior and decision-making (Stasser & Davis, 1981). The finding by Liu et al. (2022) may be explained by the fact that when group cues are present, more cooperative efforts are proposed, making threatening messages or situations become less effective. For this reason, it is expected that the inclusion of injunctive-norms elements will make the effect of fear appeals on behavioral intention weaker, whereas when no appeal is included, the effect on behavioral intention will increase. Injunctive norms, indeed, contain major group cues compared to descriptive norms,

as they are enacted by people's perceptions as a consequence of some external or internal social cue (Voisin et al., 2020).

Research by Farias (2020) demonstrated that the positive effect fear appeals have on behavioral intention becomes negative when subjective norms are present, such that intention decreases rather than increases. Subjective norms are defined by Ham et al. (2015, p. 740) as "the belief that an important person or group of people will approve and support a particular behavior". Therefore, the definition of subjective norms overlaps with that of injunctive norms, as both terms refer to an impression - or belief - that a certain behavior will be approved or not by others in a social context. When exposed to fear-inducing messages, individuals may feel motivated to engage in the recommended behavior to reduce or avoid the anticipated negative consequences (Janis & Feshbach, 1953). However, the study by Farias (2020) found that the presence of subjective norms introduces social expectations into the decision-making process. If individuals perceive that the social norm or expectation is contrary to the behavior advocated by the fear appeal, it can negatively influence behavioral intention (Farias, 2020). To conclude, research by Farias (2020) is taken as support for the expectation that injunctive norms combined with fear appeals will make sustainable eating behavior decrease rather than increase.

H2: The effect of appeal type in the ad on sustainable eating intention is moderated by social norm elements of the ad, such that (a) for descriptive norm elements in the ad, fear appeals lead to a stronger sustainable eating intention than humor appeals and no appeal, and (b) for injunctive norm elements, both humor appeals and no appeals lead to a stronger sustainable eating intention than fear appeals.

Figure 1

Conceptual model

Method

Participants

The only exclusion criterium for the targeted population regarded the age of participants, who had to be at least 18 years old to participate, whilst no particular inclusion criteria were specified. Participants were recruited through a convenience sampling strategy online and a minimum of 180 participants was required (i.e., 30 per condition). The final sample obtained from the data collection ($N = 197$) was reached after roughly three weeks. After cleaning the data, 4 units were excluded from the data set as they declared to be under 18 years old, resulting in 193 participants ranging from 18 to 65 years old ($M = 27.70$, $SD = 12.46$), of which 36.5% were males, 61.9% females, and 0.5% non-binary/third gender (1% preferred not to say and was declared as missing value for the variable ‘gender’).

To recruit participants, the link to the experiment (generated via Qualtrics.com) was shared on various social media platforms (e.g., Instagram, Facebook, LinkedIn...), as well as forwarded to the researcher’s network via WhatsApp. After ten days, a reminder was sent out on Instagram and via WhatsApp. Moreover, applying a snowball sampling strategy, people who received the link were asked to share it with their personal networks. A further step to gather more participants consisted of generating a QR code that would redirect to the survey’s link and asking people in public places (e.g., gym, university, library...) to scan it and – if willing – to participate in the experiment. Finally, the survey was published on

SurveyCircle.com, where other researchers would share their surveys as well, and everyone would support each other in need of participants.

Design

Because this research aimed to investigate a causal relationship between the use of emotional appeals and sustainable eating intention, the hypotheses of the proposed study were tested by means of an experimental method. A 3 (appeal type in the ad: humor appeal vs. fear appeal vs. no appeal) x 2 (social norm elements in the ad: injunctive norm elements vs. descriptive norm elements) between-groups factorial design was used. Therefore, six conditions in total were formed.

Procedure

The online questionnaire was created via Qualtrics.com (access granted by University of Amsterdam) and required approximately 6 minutes to be completed. Responses were made anonymous by a security feature on Qualtrics. Moreover, to assure more internal reliability, all the questions were forced responses.

Once participants opened the link, they were directed to the online questionnaire where they were first shown the consent to agree to and then asked a few demographic questions (i.e., age and gender). Participants who stated to be under 18 years old were then checked as missing data during the analyses' preparatory steps. Before being exposed to the stimulus, two questions serving as control variables were displayed (i.e., sustainable eating awareness and medical condition). Then, each participant was randomly assigned to one of the six conditions through a random assignment on Qualtrics. Afterward, participants were asked to answer a series of questions aimed to measure the dependent variable (i.e., sustainable eating intention). Four questions serving as a manipulation check were presented at the end of the survey, after which participants were thanked for their time and participation and shortly debriefed about the fake nature of the information used for the social norm elements in the ads.

Research material

Pre-test

To check whether the stimuli were effectively understood as intended by the researcher, a pilot study was conducted before the final one. A small sample of 12 participants was recruited and asked to complete the survey draft generated via Qualtrics.com. Participants were randomly assigned to one of the six conditions, such that in the end each level had two participants. After being exposed to the stimulus, participants answered the manipulation check questions, i.e. 1) To what extent do you think the ad was inducing fear?; 2) To what extent do you think the ad was humorous?; 3) To what extent did the ad describe how other people behave?; 4) To what extent did the ad make you think about how you should behave to be accepted by other people?. They were able to answer each question on a scale from 1 (*not at all*) to 7 (*extremely*).

Subsequently, a manipulation check was performed on SPSS by means of a Two-Way ANOVA. Fear, humor, and no appeals were unsuccessfully manipulated, as they were all perceived to induce equal fear, $F(2,6) = 1.72, p = .257$, and to be equally humorous, $F(2,6) = 4.13, p = .074$. Injunctive norms were also unsuccessfully manipulated ($F(1,6) = .90, p = .379$), while only descriptive norms were perceived as intended, $F(1,6) = 66.67, p = <.001$.

Therefore, feedback regarding the stimuli was directly asked of the participants. The relevant adjustments consisted of changing the fear appeals, as they were not clear and fearful enough to the participants, and changing the wording of some sentences. The quality of the advertisements was improved accordingly to participants' feedback, and the final version of the survey was published.

Stimuli

The finalized experiment stimuli consisted of six images entirely crafted by the researcher via the free website Canva (see Appendix B). Each image represents an advertisement promoting sustainable eating and has the same green background and a recycling logo on one of the corners. The only difference between the six images concerns the manipulation of both the "appeal type in the ad" and "social norm elements in the ad" variables.

The six images are distinguished between two having fear appeals, two having humor appeals, and two having no appeals (see Appendix B). The ads containing a fear appeal are text-based only and contain a message that aimed to trigger participants' sensibility toward the negative consequences of not adopting a sustainable diet. On the other hand, the stimuli with a humor appeal were structured as a meme, therefore having both text and two images. The images were the same for the two conditions using humor, while the text was adapted based on either the descriptive or injunctive norm. The 'no appeal' stimuli contained only text, and the tone of the message was kept as neutral and informative as possible.

Three of the stimuli have descriptive norm elements, which were included as statistical data (i.e., 94% of people...) referring to a description of what other people do. In combination with the descriptive elements, the ad also contained either a fear appeal, a humor appeal, or no appeal. The same applies to the remaining three stimuli, which have injunctive norm elements instead. Injunctive elements were included as a subtle way to redirect participants toward how they thought other people would judge their behavior (e.g., "What would your friend say about you being the only one not eating sustainable food?").

Measures

Appeal type in the ad

In this study, the independent variable (viz., appeal type in the ad) is a manifest variable with three categorical levels and is measured on a nominal level. Appeal type in the ad refers to the presence of a specific emotional appeal in advertisements aimed at influencing people's attitudes and perceptions. In this study, the variable represents three distinct conditions: the use of humor appeals, the use of fear appeals, and the absence of any appeal.

Social norm elements

The moderator (i.e., social norm elements in the ad) is also a manifest variable measured at the nominal level with two groups, specifically: 1) descriptive norm elements, 2) injunctive norm elements. The variable refers to the inclusion or depiction of social norms within an advertisement and can be distinguished between descriptive and injunctive norms.

Sustainable eating intention

The dependent variable (i.e., sustainable eating intention) was measured by means of a scale adapted from Tobler et al. (2011). The existing scale consisted of five items (i.e., 1. Buy regional food, 2. Eat only seasonal fruits and vegetables, 3. Eat less meat (maximum once or twice per week), 4. Avoid food products that were imported by airplane, 5. Buy organic food), and four response categories at the nominal level. The original answer options included: (1) I am not doing this and I am not willing to; (2) I would like to do this, but I do not know how; (3) I would like to do this, and I already know how to start; (4) I am doing this already. For the purposes of the current study, the measurement level of the scale was transformed into a numerical one, by replacing the original answer categories with a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 7 (*strongly agree*). Participants were therefore asked to what extent they agreed with the five statements.

A principal axis factor analysis (PAF) showed that the five items relied on one underlying dimension, as only one factor was extracted above the point of inflexion (i.e., Eigenvalue = 2.87). The factor explains 57.49% of the items' total variance. A reliability analysis was consequently conducted, showing a good scale reliability (Cronbach's alpha = .81, $M = 24.29$, $SD = 6.00$). The mean of the scale was then computed to create a new variable labeled "sustainable eating intention" that would be used as the dependent variable for further analyses.

Control variables

Some control variables were assessed in the questionnaire, namely, participants were asked about their: 1) Awareness of sustainable eating impact on the environment and 2) Medical conditions that may influence eating habits. The first control variable (i.e., awareness) was measured on a 7-point scale ranging from 1 (*not at all*) to 7 (*extremely*) and asked: "To what extent do you think sustainable diets have a significant impact on the environment?". On the other hand, medical conditions of participants were measured on a nominal level by asking "(If you are comfortable to share) Are you currently following a diet that has been specifically prescribed for you as a consequence of medical circumstances?"

and by making three answer options available (i.e., 1. Yes, I am; 2. No, my dietary choices are not affected by medical conditions; 3. Prefer not to say)

Manipulation check (questions)

Four questions in total were asked at the end of the questionnaire to verify whether the manipulations were perceived as intended by the researcher. All participants, regardless of the condition they were exposed to, were asked respectively: “To what extent do you think the ad was inducing fear?” and “To what extent do you think the ad was humorous?” to check for the independent variable manipulation. On the next page, participants were asked respectively: “To what extent did the ad make you think about how you should behave to be accepted by other people?” and “To what extent did the ad only describe how other people actually behave?”. They were able to answer each question on a scale from 1 (*not at all*) to 7 (*extremely*).

Results

Manipulation checks

First, the manipulation checks were statistically verified with One-Way ANOVA analyses. Each variable measuring whether the manipulation was perceived as intended at the end of the questionnaire was used as a dependent variable in each analysis, with the variables appeal type and social norm elements as factors. The homogeneity of variances could be assumed for the first model measuring perceived fear, $F(5,163) = 0.44, p = .824$, for the second one measuring perceived humor, $F(5,163) = 1.46, p = .205$, for the third one measuring perceived injunctive norms, $F(5,160) = 0.26, p = .934$, and for the fourth one measuring perceived descriptive norms, $F(5,160) = 2.14, p = .063$.

The manipulation check for fear appeal showed a significant difference across groups on the factor of appeal type, $F(2,163) = 8.13, p < .001$. A Bonferroni post hoc test revealed that people in the fear conditions performed significantly higher ($M = 4.35, SD = 1.73$) than those in the humor appeal ($M = 3.37, SD = 1.55, p = .005$) or no appeal conditions ($M = 3.18, SD = 1.65, p < .001$). The manipulation check for fear appeals was successful.

The manipulation check for humor appeal showed a significant difference across groups on the factor of appeal type, $F(2,163) = 25.97, p < .001$. People in the humor

conditions performed significantly higher ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 1.66$) than those in the fear appeal ($M = 2.05$, $SD = 1.47$, $p = <.001$) or no appeal conditions ($M = 2.62$, $SD = 1.48$, $p = <.001$). The manipulation check for humor appeals was successful.

The manipulation check for injunctive norms showed a significant difference across groups on the factor of social norm elements, $F(1,160) = 9.56$, $p = .002$. People in the injunctive conditions performed significantly higher ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 1.69$) than those in the descriptive groups ($M = 3.30$, $SD = 1.69$). The manipulation check for injunctive norm elements was successful.

Finally, the manipulation check for descriptive norms showed a significant difference across groups on the factor of social norm elements, $F(1,160) = 7.73$, $p = .006$. People in the descriptive conditions performed significantly higher ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 1.87$) than those in the injunctive ones ($M = 3.21$, $SD = 1.53$). The manipulation check for descriptive norm elements was successful.

Randomization checks

Consequently, a randomization check was performed for each control variable (i.e., age, gender, sustainable eating awareness, medical condition) to verify whether such variables systematically differed across conditions. Firstly, a One-Way ANOVA showed a non-significant relationship between age and the six conditions, $F(5,178) = 0.73$, $p = .605$. Therefore, the null hypothesis that age does not systematically differ across conditions is retained, demonstrating that the randomization was successful and that age is not a possible confounder. Secondly, the same statistical test was used with sustainable eating awareness as the dependent variable. The output showed no significant difference, meaning the null hypothesis is retained, $F(5,181) = 1.45$, $p = .207$. Similarly, the result shows that awareness about sustainable eating does not systematically differ across conditions. Therefore, the randomization was again successful and the variable is not a possible confounder.

A Chi-Square analysis was then performed between gender and the conditions ($N = 186$), resulting in a non-significant correlation ($p = .798$). Once again, the randomization check turned out successful as gender does not systematically differ across conditions. Finally, the control variable regarding medical conditions that could affect participants' eating choices was checked for by means of a Chi-Square analysis, which revealed a non-significant

effect ($p = .475$). Participants did not differ across conditions in terms of their personal medical condition regarding eating habits. All randomization checks were successful.

Hypotheses testing

Hypothesis 1

To test the hypotheses of this study, a Two-Way ANOVA was run. The selected analysis allows for the main effects' testing as well as testing the interaction effect between the independent variable and the moderator on the dependent variable. Because some participants dropped out before answering the questions to measure their sustainable eating intention, the sample interested in the following analyses is 175 participants.

H1: The use of fear appeals in ads about sustainable eating leads to a stronger sustainable eating intention compared to humor appeals and no appeals.

First, H1 was tested. The output showed that the appeal type in the ad has a non-significant effect on sustainable eating intention, $F(2,169) = 2.06$, $p = .130$. The effect size, eta squared (η^2), was 0.024, indicating a very weak effect. A Bonferroni post-hoc test revealed that there is no significant difference between fear appeals ($M = 5.11$, $SD = 1.18$) and humor appeals ($M = 4.74$, $SD = 1.17$, $p = .272$), as well as no appeals ($M = 4.71$, $SD = 1.23$, $p = .234$). Considering these results, the assumption that fear appeals lead to higher sustainable eating intention compared to humor and no appeals (i.e., H1) must be rejected.

Hypothesis 2

H2: The effect of appeal type in the ad on sustainable eating intention is moderated by social norm elements of the ad, such that (a) for descriptive norm elements in the ad, fear appeals lead to a stronger sustainable eating intention than humor appeals and no appeal, and (b) for injunctive norm elements, both humor appeals and no appeals lead to a stronger sustainable eating intention than fear appeals.

The same analysis was used to answer H2 and showed that there is no significant interaction effect between the independent variable and moderator, $F(2,169) = 0.24$, $p = .786$. The effect size, eta squared (η^2), was 0.003, indicating a very weak effect. Participants

exposed to the descriptive-fear ad ($M = 5.25$, $SD = 1.24$) did not report a significantly higher sustainable eating intention than participants in the descriptive-humor condition ($M = 4.72$, $SD = 1.26$) and than those in the descriptive-only condition ($M = 4.79$, $SD = 1.25$).

As well, participants in the injunctive-humor condition ($M = 4.75$, $SD = 1.11$) did not score significantly higher on sustainable eating intention than those exposed to the injunctive-fear ad ($M = 4.98$, $SD = 1.12$) and those in the injunctive-only condition ($M = 4.64$, $SD = 1.22$). To summarize, H2 is not supported (see Figure 2 for an overview of the interaction). Despite not being strong enough to be statistically significant, however, Figure 2 would suggest that, as hypothesized, when fear appeals are associated with descriptive norm elements, sustainable eating intention is higher than when descriptive norms are associated with humor appeals or no appeals.

Figure 2

Interaction effect “appeal type of the ad” and “social norm elements”.

Conclusion

To conclude, there is no meaningful difference in using humor, fear, or no appeals when aiming to increase one's sustainable eating intention. At the same time, when implementing social norm elements (i.e., injunctive or descriptive) in an advertisement either using or not using these emotional appeals, the previous relationship does not significantly differ, such that sustainable eating intention is neither decreased nor increased. However, as shown in Figure 2, a small interaction between social norm elements and appeal type happens at the level of humor appeals. This would suggest that, when humor appeals are used, injunctive and descriptive norms may have the same influence on sustainable eating intention, while descriptive norms tend to slightly increase intention when combined with fear or no appeals.

By exploring the effects of fear and humor appeals, this study contributes to expanding knowledge on emotional appeals' use, specifically in the context of sustainable eating. The results add to previous literature by demonstrating that, when aiming at influencing immediate behavioral intentions, there is no difference in the effects of fear appeals, humor appeals, or no appeals in advertisements. This study expands the findings of Farias (2020) by specifically examining the use of fear appeals in the context of sustainable - rather than healthy - eating. Fear appeals' effects in the health domain may indeed differ from those in the sustainable domain, and this difference might serve as one possible explanation for the contradictory results.

Similarly, the investigation of social norm elements as a moderator adds to the existing literature about the different effects of descriptive and injunctive norms on behavioral intention. Park and Smith (2007) stressed the great influence of both norms on intention. However, this study adds to the two authors' findings by demonstrating that social norms are not strong predictors of behavioral intention (i.e., in the context of sustainable eating) when combined with fear, humor, or no appeal.

Discussion

Limitations

This study includes several limitations that must be addressed. Firstly, the sample cannot be considered representative because of the recruitment procedure (i.e., convenience

sampling). The sampling technique applied in the current research, though convenient, may not have guaranteed a diverse and unbiased representation of the wider population, thus limiting the generalizability of the results. Additionally, conducting the experiment online excluded individuals without Internet access, potentially introducing selection bias. Furthermore, the lack of control over the online experiment may have negatively contributed to the outcomes, as participants may have responded without the required attention and effort.

Secondly, the study focuses on immediate effects and intentions rather than long-term behavioral changes. Accordingly, the exposure to the experiment stimuli may have been too short to concretely affect people's behavioral intention. Moreover, the reliance on self-report measures to assess sustainable eating intention introduces the possibility of response bias. Participants may have provided socially desirable responses, or their intentions may have not accurately reflected their behaviors.

Lastly, the current study included control variables that were potentially inadequate to capture all relevant external factors that might have influenced participants' sustainable eating intention. This limitation stems from the inability to entirely assess the causal nature of the experimental design employed because of the lack of control for all possible confounders. For example, factors like prior sustainable eating intention, personal values, or financial availability could have possibly impacted the outcomes of the study.

Recommendations

Future researchers who wish to conduct a follow-up study are advised to conduct a longitudinal experiment to examine the long-term effects of different emotional appeals in advertising on sustainable eating intention. This will help determine if the observed effects are sustainable over time and whether there are any unexpected changes in behavior over longer periods. In addition, participants' previous sustainable eating intention should be measured before exposing them to one of the stimuli, to increase the control and internal validity of the study. Additionally, future researchers may use more objective measures (e.g., food consumption records) to validate the effectiveness of emotional appeals and social norms in influencing sustainable eating practices. Finally, this study examined fear and humor, but various other emotional appeals could be investigated. Future research could

compare stimuli such as hope, inspiration, empathy, or disgust, to determine their relative effectiveness in promoting sustainable eating intention.

Altogether, this research has helped stress the importance of sustainable food consumption in the current society and has explored the effects of relevant persuasive strategies in advertising on individuals' behavioral intention about the issue. This study may serve as a starting point to investigate what effective strategies to use to successfully target sustainable eating intention.

References

- Beverland, M. B. (2014). Sustainable eating. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 34(3), 369–382. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0276146714526410>
- Dietrich, C. (2010). Decision Making: Factors that Influence Decision Making, Heuristics Used, and Decision Outcomes. *Inquiries Journal*, 2(02).
- European Climate Pact. (2022, July 28). *Eating sustainably – easier than you think?* https://climate-pact.europa.eu/news/eating-sustainably-easier-you-think-2022-07-28_en
- Farías, P. (2020). The use of fear versus hope in health advertisements: The moderating role of individual characteristics on subsequent health decisions in Chile. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(23), 9148. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17239148>
- Gelfand, M. J., & Harrington, J. R. (2015). The motivational force of descriptive norms. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 46(10), 1273–1278. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022115600796>
- Ham, M., Jeger, M., & Ivković, A. (2015). The role of subjective norms in forming the intention to purchase green food. *Ekonomiska Istrazivanja-Economic Research*, 28(1), 738–748. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677x.2015.1083875>
- Holbrook, M. B., & O’Shaughnessy, J. (1984). The role of emotion in advertising. *Psychology & Marketing*, 1(2), 45–64. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.4220010206>
- Jäger, T., & Eisend, M. (2013). Effects of fear-arousing and humorous appeals in social marketing advertising: The moderating role of prior attitude toward the advertised behavior. *Journal of Current Issues and Research in Advertising*, 34(1), 125–134. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10641734.2013.754718>
- Janis, I. L., & Feshbach, S. (1953). Effects of fear-arousing communications. *The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 48(1), 78–92. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0060732>
- Leventhal, H. (1971). Fear appeals and persuasion: the differentiation of a motivational construct. *American Journal of Public Health*, 61(6), 1208–1224. <https://doi.org/10.2105/ajph.61.6.1208>
- Lim, J. R., Liu, B. F., & Seate, A. A. (2022). Are you prepared for the next storm? Developing social norms messages to motivate community members to perform

- disaster risk mitigation behaviors. *Risk Analysis*, 42(11), 2550–2568. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.13957>
- Liu, J., Yang, X., Lu, Y., & Zheng, X. (2022). The joint effects of social norm appeals and fear appeals in COVID-19 vaccine campaign posters on self-perceived communication quality and vaccination intention. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.760146>
- McKimmie, B. M. (2015). Cognitive Dissonance in Groups. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 9(4), 202–212. <https://doi.org/10.1111/spc3.12167>
- Melnyk, V., Van Herpen, E., Fischer, A. R., & Van Trijp, H. C. (2013). Regulatory fit effects for injunctive versus descriptive social norms: Evidence from the promotion of sustainable products. *Marketing Letters*, 24(2), 191–203. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11002-013-9234-5>
- Melnyk, V., Van Herpen, E., & Van Trijp, J. (2010). The Influence of Social Norms in Consumer Decision Making: a Meta-Analysis. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 37, 463–464. https://www.acrwebsite.org/volumes/v37/acr_v37_15187.pdf
- Meyer, J. S., & Venette, S. J. (2017). Humor in Health and Risk Messaging. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Communication*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228613.013.507>
- Meyer, J. S. (2000). Humor as a double-edged sword: Four functions of humor in communication. *Communication Theory*, 10(3), 310–331. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2885.2000.tb00194.x>
- Mifdal, M. (2022). Covidly humorous memes. *The European Journal of Humour Research*, 10(3), 189–210. <https://doi.org/10.7592/ejhr.2022.10.3.688>
- Parekh, V. S., & Svenfelt, Å. (2022). Taking sustainable eating practices from niche to mainstream: the perspectives of Swedish food-provisioning actors on barriers and potentials. *Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy*, 18(1), 292–308. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15487733.2022.2044197>
- Park, H. C., & Smith, S. W. (2007). Distinctiveness and influence of subjective norms, personal descriptive and injunctive norms, and societal descriptive and injunctive norms on behavioral intent: A case of two behaviors critical to organ donation. *Human*

- Communication Research*, 33(2), 194–218. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2958.2007.00296.x>
- Pristl, A. C., Kilian, S., & Mann, A. (2021). When does a social norm catch the worm? Disentangling social normative influences on sustainable consumption behaviour. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 20(3), 635–654. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cb.1890>
- Salmivaara, L., Lombardini, C., & Lankoski, L. (2021). Examining social norms among other motives for sustainable food choice: The promise of descriptive norms. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 311, 127508. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127508>
- Sanfey, A. G., Stallen, M., & Chang, L. S. (2014). Norms and expectations in social decision-making. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 18(4), 172–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2014.01.011>
- Skurka, C., Niederdeppe, J., Romero-Canyas, R., & Acup, D. (2018). Pathways of influence in emotional appeals: Benefits and tradeoffs of using fear or humor to promote climate change-related intentions and risk perceptions. *Journal of Communication*, 68(1), 169–193. <https://doi.org/10.1093/joc/jqx008>
- Tobler, C., Visschers, V. H., & Siegrist, M. (2011). Eating green. Consumers' willingness to adopt ecological food consumption behaviors. *Appetite*, 57(3), 674–682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2011.08.010>
- Tran, J. M., Paprzcki, P. P., Copa, C. E., Castor, T. S., Diehr, A. J., & Glassman, T. (2021). Social norms vs. fear appeals: Mixing alcohol with prescription drugs – a message testing study. *Substance Use & Misuse*, 56(9), 1397–1402. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10826084.2021.1928212>
- USDA. (2022, January 24). *Food Waste and its Links to Greenhouse Gases and Climate Change*. <https://www.usda.gov/media/blog/2022/01/24/food-waste-and-its-links-greenhouse-gases-and-climate-change>
- Van Breda, L., Terblanche-Smit, M., & Pelser, T. (2023). The effectiveness of sustainability social marketing use of fear and guilt appeals to influence the behavioural intention of millennials. *European Business Review*, 35(2), 202–222. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ebr-05-2022-0080>
- Van Der Pligt, J., & Vliek, M. (2016). *The Psychology of Influence: Theory, research and practice*. Taylor & Francis.

- Verbeke, W., Hoefkens, C., & Verbeke, W. (2017). Healthy, sustainable and plant-based eating: Perceived (mis)match and involvement-based consumer segments as targets for future policy. *Food Policy*, *69*, 46–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2017.03.001>
- Vermeir, I., Weijters, B., De Houwer, J., Geuens, M., Slabbinck, H., Spruyt, A., Van Kerckhove, A., Van Lippevelde, W., De Steur, H., & Verbeke, W. (2020). Environmentally sustainable food consumption: A review and research agenda from a goal-directed perspective. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *11*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01603>
- Voisin, D., Gosling, P., Amoura, C., Miraucourt, D., Weber, T., & Dappe, Q. (2020). If They Are All Green, I Take Responsibility for My Eco-Unfriendly Behaviors: Effects of Injunctive Norm on Sense of Responsibility Following Cognitive Dissonance. *Revue Internationale De Psychologie Sociale*, *33*(1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/irsp.113>
- Witte, K. (1994). Fear control and danger control: A test of the extended parallel process model (EPPM). *Communication Monographs*, *61*(2), 113–134. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03637759409376328>

Appendix A: Questionnaire

Dear participant,

First, thank you for your interest in participating in this research project! Before the experiment starts, it is important that you are well-informed about the procedure. Therefore, we would like you to read this information letter carefully. Please do not hesitate to ask for clarification about this text or the general procedure. If anything is unclear, the researcher will gladly answer your questions.

The current research is about creative appeals together with social norms in advertisements and sustainable eating intention.

Participation in the study entails no considerable risks or inconveniences. Participation in this study takes approximately 6 to 7 minutes.

As this research is being carried out under the responsibility of The Amsterdam School of Communication Research (ASCoR), which is part of the University of Amsterdam (UvA), we can guarantee that:

A) Your personal information (about who you are) remains confidential and will not be shared without your explicit consent. Your research data will be analyzed to answer the research question as described above in the goal of this study. Note that that further processing of your data is possible, provided that this is compatible with this purpose. Research data published in scientific journals will be anonymous and cannot be traced back to you as an individual. Finally: - Completely anonymized data can be shared with other researchers.

- Completely anonymized data can be made publicly accessible.

B) No later than four months after completion of the study, you can obtain a summary of the research results. If you wish to receive this, please send an e-mail to the researcher (see below).

For more information about the research you are welcome to contact the researcher Alessia Zenobio, alessia.zenobio@student.uva.nl.

Should you have any complaints or comments about the course of the research and the

procedures it involves as a consequence of your participation in this research, you can contact the designated member of the Ethics Review Board representing ASCoR via ascor-secr-fmg@uva.nl

Any complaints or comments will be treated in the strictest confidence.

I hope to have provided you with sufficient information. I would like to take this opportunity to thank you in advance for your assistance with this research, which I greatly appreciate.

Kind regards, Alessia Zenobio

Default Question Block

If you would like to participate in the survey, click on “Yes” below. With this you declare:

- I am 16 years or older.
 - I have read and understood the information.
 - I agree to participate in the study and to use the data obtained with it.
 - I reserve the right to withdraw this consent without giving any reason.
 - I reserve the right to stop the study at any time I wish
- Yes, I participate
- No, I am not participating

Block 1: Demographics

1) What is your age? Please, indicate the age of your latest birthday in numbers (e.g., 18).

2) What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary / third gender
- Prefer not to say

Block 2: Control variables

1) On a scale from 1 (*not at all*) to 7 (*extremely*), please select the most appropriate response for you according to the statement below. (Slider from 1 = not at all, to 7 = extremely)

- To what extent do you think sustainable diets have a significant impact on the environment?

2) (If you are comfortable to share) Are you currently following a diet that has been specifically prescribed for you as a consequence of medical circumstances?

- Yes, I am

- No, my dietary choices are not affected by medical conditions

- Prefer not to say

Block 3: introduction to stimulus

On the next page, please take some time to carefully observe the following advertisement about sustainable eating. After 10 seconds, the button to go on will appear. When you are ready to continue, please select the button to go on.

(In the next page):

One of the six stimuli is shown in a random manner. A timer of 10 seconds is put on Qualtrics for each of the stimuli (for the experiment stimuli, see appendix B)

Block 4: DV measurement

1) On a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree), to what extent do you agree on taking the following actions in the future?

matrix table with answer options: 1) strongly disagree, 2) disagree, 3) somewhat disagree, 4) neither agree nor disagree, 5) somewhat agree, 6) agree, 7) strongly agree.

3) Buy regional food

4) Eat only seasonal fruits and vegetables

5) Eat less meat (maximum once or twice per week)

6) Avoid food products that were imported by airplane

7) Buy organic food

Block 5: Manipulation checks

1) On a scale from 1 (*not at all*) to 7 (*extremely*), please select the most appropriate response for you according to the statement below. (Slider from 1 = not at all, to 7 = extremely)

- To what extent do you think the ad was inducing fear?

2) On a scale from 1 (*not at all*) to 7 (*extremely*), please select the most appropriate response for you according to the statement below. (Slider from 1 = not at all, to 7 = extremely)

- To what extent do you think the ad was humorous?

3) On a scale from 1 (*not at all*) to 7 (*extremely*), please select the most appropriate response for you according to the statement below. (Slider from 1 = not at all, to 7 = extremely)

- To what extent do you think the ad was making you think about how you should behave to be accepted by other people?

4) On a scale from 1 (*not at all*) to 7 (*extremely*), please select the most appropriate response for you according to the statement below. (Slider from 1 = not at all, to 7 = extremely)

- To what extent do you think the ad was describing how other people behave?

Block 6

Finally, please select the option that suits you best for what concerns the use of your **anonymized** data for the purposes of the study only.

- By clicking this box, I AGREE to participate in this study and to submit my data for analysis.
- By clicking this box, I DO NOT agree to participate in this study and submit my data for analysis.

End of survey: Debriefing message

Dear participants,

As the researcher of this study, I would like to again thank you for your help and further inform you that some of the information you have been exposed to does not reflect real data. More specifically, if the image that was presented to you contained some description of

socially relevant data (e.g., 94% of **people** globally have already decided to adopt a sustainable diet), I must inform you that the text was crafted for the purpose of the study only.

Appendix B: Experiment stimuli

1. Descriptive-fear condition:

2. Descriptive-humor condition:

94% of people (who eat sustainable food):

other people (not eating sustainable food):

don't be like other people, eat sustainable food!

3. Descriptive-only condition:

94% of people globally have already decided to adopt a sustainable diet.

Be part of the change!

4. Injunctive-fear condition:

Not only is non-sustainable food full of chemicals and toxic residues that may poison you, but it also contributes to the climate change crisis.

What would other people think if you were the only one who doesn't eat sustainable food to minimise this crisis?

Don't risk being left out.

**Be part of the change!
Eat sustainable food.**

5. Injunctive-humor condition:

everyone else (eating sustainable food):

you (if you are not eating sustainable food):

don't be left out, eat sustainable food!

6. Injunctive-only condition:

**What would other people
think if you were the only
one who doesn't eat
sustainable food?**

Don't risk being left out.

**Be part of the change!
Eat sustainable food.**